

AMIR TEMUR IN THE DEPICTIONS OF EUROPEANS

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Annotation. This article analyzes the image of Amir Temur in European depictions based on the work “*Menkim, Sahibqiran — Conqueror Temur*” by the French writer Marcel Brion. The work presents the qualities of Sahibqiran as a statesman, skilled military commander, and patron of science and enlightenment through the memoirs of the Christian bishop of Sultaniya. The article provides a scholarly interpretation of how Amir Temur’s imperial power, military mastery, strict governance policy, wealth, and personal courage are portrayed from the bishop’s perspective. The study concludes that in the European author’s depiction, Amir Temur appears as a just, powerful, and one of the bravest rulers of his era.

Keywords: Amir Temur, Marcel Brion, Sahibqiran, historical image, bishop’s memoirs, European perspective, military leadership, state governance.

AMIR TEMUR BOBOMIZ YEVROPALIKLAR TASVIRIDA

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Amir Temur shaxsining yevropaliklar tasviridagi obrazi fransuz adibi Marcel Brionning “Menkim, sohibqiron — jahongir Temur” asari asosida tahlil qilinadi. Asarda Sultoniya shahrining nasroniy episkopi esdaliklari orqali Sohibqironning davlat arbobi, mohir sarkarda hamda ilm-ma’rifat homiysi sifatidagi fazilatlarini yoritib berilgan. Maqolada Amir Temurning saltanat qudrati, harbiy mahorati, qat’iy boshqaruv siyosati, boyligi va shaxsiy jasorati episkop nigohida qanday talqin etilgani ilmiy jihatdan asoslab beriladi. Tadqiqot natijasida yevropalik muallif tasvirida Amir Temur obrazi adolatparvar, qudratli va o‘z davrining eng jasur hukmdorlaridan biri sifatida namoyon bo‘lishi xulosalanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Amir Temur, Marsel Brion, Sohibqiron, tarixiy obraz, episkop esdaliklari, yevropaliklar nigohi, sarkardalik, davlat boshqaruvi.

АМИР ТЕМУР В ИЗОБРАЖЕНИИ ЕВРОПЕЙЦЕВ

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Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется образ Амир Темур в изображении европейцев на основе произведения французского писателя Марсель Брион «Menkim, Сахибкиран — завоеватель Темур». В произведении через воспоминания христианского епископа города Султания раскрываются качества Сахибкирана как государственного деятеля, талантливого полководца и покровителя науки и просвещения. В статье с научной точки зрения анализируется трактовка могущества державы Амира Темура, его военного мастерства, строгой политики управления, богатства и личной храбрости в восприятии епископа. В результате исследования делается вывод о том, что в изображении европейского автора Амир Темур предстаёт как справедливый, могущественный и один из самых отважных правителей своей эпохи.

Ключевые слова: Амир Темур, Марсель Брион, Сахибкиран, исторический образ, воспоминания епископа, взгляд европейцев, полководческое искусство, государственное управление.

Among the works written about Amir Timur, Marcel Brion's memoir “I, the Ohibqiron – the Conqueror Timur” holds a special place. This book has occupied a worthy spot on our bookshelves for many years.

The book is, of course, about our great-ancestor Amir Timur. However, it is fitting to first focus on the author of the work. Marcel Brion was a French writer, historian, and literary scholar. He was born in Marseille on November 21, 1895, and died in Paris on October 23, 1984. Although he began his career as a lawyer, his interest in literature prevailed. He then began to write historical novels.

His decision to write a novel about Amir Timur was prompted by sources he found in the Bibliothèque Nationale de France. In particular, Marcel Brion is drawn to the valuable memoirs written by the Christian bishop of the city of Sultaniyeh, based on his intense conversations with Amir Timur Ko'ragoniy. The author finds these very sources, is inspired by them, and creates a work about the Great Amir.

He writes that the Christian bishop of the city of Sultaniyeh sought out Amir Timur and lived in his presence for several years. He recounts in a memoir style what he saw with his own eyes and the authentic, historical events he gathered about the Amir Temur. As we read these memoirs, we feel as if we are witnessing certain chapters of Amir Temur's life firsthand.

On page 18 of the book, Amir Timur also specifically highlights his conversation with the Christian bishop of the city of Sultaniya, stating, "My conversation with the bishop of Sultaniya..." This shows that the bishop's writings have a historical basis.

Thus, the Bishop of Sultaniya describes Amir Timur in his memoirs as follows: "His name is Temurbek. The word 'Temur' means metal (iron), and 'bek' means ruler. His enemies call him 'Temurlang,' because one of his legs is lame. In Iran, Temurbek is also called 'Miri tabam' — 'Great Leader.'"

Throughout the work, through the bishop, the author also speaks of Amir Timur's sons and grandchildren, describing them with affection and respect.

Episcopus's main focus is on portraying the personality of Amir Timur: "Temurbek, although quite old at the time of the meeting, was still physically strong, resilient to the hardships of travel, and active in battles. He spends his days and nights in the boundless steppes, under the open sky. It is said that in his youth, Temurbek was an exceptionally handsome and charming young man. Some traces of that handsome appearance were still clearly visible in his present form and exterior."

In the main part of his memoirs, Episkop describes the wealth of Amir Timur in detail and with great effect:

His wealth is immeasurable, beyond counting. If the gold coins in his treasury were scattered, they could cover the entire face of the earth... His empire is boundless: a traveler

would need a year's journey to go from one end of his domain to the other. Complete security was ensured over these distances. From ordinary travelers to trade caravans, they moved freely along these roads."

Through these descriptions, the bishop emphasizes that Amir Timur's empire was not only a rich and powerful state but also one where order, discipline, and security were firmly established.

At this point, the bishop also notes that the Amir Timur was a strict ruler:

"Should a raid or plundering by robbers occur in any region, Amir Timur would first have the local governor of that region executed. For," the bishop explains, "in Tamerlane's view, if a local governor did not collude with bandits and performed his duties conscientiously and honestly, no bandit gang would dare to rob on the main roads."

These observations indicate that Amir Timur relied on the principles of strict discipline and personal accountability in his state administration.

The bishop also makes special note of Amir Timur's abilities as a commander:

"From the very first day he came to power until now, all of Tamerlane's campaigns have been victorious: there is no ruler or fortress that has not surrendered to him."

Elsewhere, he writes:

"Temurbek, if he wishes, can assemble a 100,000-man army from the population under his command, composed of ten times as many men capable of fighting."

From this description, it is clear that the Great Khan's army was not only numerous but also composed of highly trained, disciplined, and physically hardened warriors.

The bishop writes the following about the personality of Amir Timur:

"Timur speaks Arabic, Persian, and Turkish fluently. He has such a deep knowledge of the science of the word and Islamic jurisprudence that no Muslim scholar has been able to defeat him in scholarly debate and discussion. Temurbek has more than 200 palaces: in Samarkand alone there are 18, in Kesh 20, in Baghdad 15, in Isfahan 12, and in Shiraz 7. In honor of his victory over Baghdad, he received a tree made of pure gold. Its leaves were adorned with precious stones, the true value of which no one could say," the bishop notes.

Regarding Tamerlane's bravery, he says:

"On the battlefield, he stands in the ranks like a common soldier, entering the fray alongside everyone else. He does not fear death. Although he has been wounded not once, but several times, and has faced death many times, he has never once retreated. He personally leads his army into battle."

The bishop also makes a special note of the Emperor's attitude toward science and scholarship:

“He greatly values and respects scholars and poets. This is because he himself is a man of learning...”

Episcop concludes his memoirs with the following words:

“After seeing with my own eyes him enter a battle and leave it victorious, I came to the conclusion that Tamerlan, without a doubt, is the bravest man of his time!”

Conclusion

In conclusion, in the work of the European author Marcel Brion, the figure of Amir Timur is depicted not only as a formidable commander but also as a learned, just, and resolute statesman. Through the memoirs of the Bishop, the Great Conqueror's personal virtues, military skill, and firmness in state administration are vividly expressed. This shows that the personality of Amir Timur was also highly valued in the eyes of Europeans.

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